

Choosing an Academic Publication Venue: A Short Guide for Beginners

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Over the years, many students and early career researchers have asked me for advice on the complicated matter of “how do you know where to publish?”.

What follows in this document are general recommendations that might help you begin your search for a venue to submit to, clarify the difference between various publication venues, and help you identify the right one for you and your work.

Obviously, the landscape of publication outlets is huge, so this is an unavoidably generic set of pointers to begin a publication plan – also because it is difficult to give guidance that applies to every discipline or field of research.

Therefore, the first important piece of advice is to make sure to enlist the help of a colleague, supervisor or mentor (ideally from your own discipline) to discuss your options.

...So if you’ve done the work, you’re written an article (or you are working on one...or thinking about doing it!) and you are planning to submit for publication...How do you decide where do you send it?

There are many different options, and it is not always easy to identify good venues (with scientific and scholarly rigour) and venues that are right for your work and for your discipline (in terms of who will review them and read them after they are published).

1. Identify what are the valued publication venues in your field

Different disciplines have different consideration of the various types of publication. For example, in the humanities and some areas of social sciences, writing monographs is considered essential for establishing your academic track record, impact and for future promotions. In some science and technology subjects, journals (ideally with high impact factor, more on this later) are instead the main target, while monographs are not that important. In other fields, such as my own (human-computer interaction) and others within computing and engineering, certain conferences with rigorous peer review are also a main target for publication.

→ As you read and analyse the literature in your field, start keeping track of which publication venues tend to appear the most: it could be a specific set of journals, or a

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popular conference, or a particular book series that has published most of the important texts on your topic. In other words, identify where the things and authors you are reading have been published.

→ If you are looking for new publications about your topic, where are you most likely to find them? Which is linked to: where do you aspire to see your work published?

This should help you begin to form a plan for which types of publication to pursue. Naturally, throughout their career every researcher will develop a portfolio that includes a mix of publication types (from book chapters to conference papers).

This is due to many factors:

- *Opportunity*: i.e. you are invited to contribute a chapter to an edited book that will collate research related to yours; or a journal special issue is advertised on a specific topic that well matches your work.
- *Requirements*: i.e. the project/scholarship that supports you requires that you produce a particular output, such as a journal article, monograph, etc. Another requirement is that of publishing in certain venues (for example, journals of a certain rank) as dictated by criteria for tenure or promotion of academics in certain countries.
- *Type of work*: i.e. not all pieces you will write will fit into one venue. For example, you might have done some exploratory work that would benefit from feedback at a small conference or symposium, and might not yet be ready for journal publication.
- *Personal target*: i.e. you really want to make your work appear in a certain [conference; journal; symposium; magazine], so that it can be accessed by a certain audience, or benefit from its reach or prestige, for example for future job applications or promotion.

Other scenarios could be: you might have a major set of empirical data that should be written up as a monograph or as a series of journal papers, or want to write a more conceptual thought-piece on your subject for a magazine, or produce a report on a smaller case study in a conference paper.

As you plan your writing, try and identify for each piece a possible “home” in terms of publication venue.

Let’s have a look at how to navigate through the various types of venues.

2. Journals

Refereed journals are considered as some of the highest impact venues for publication in most academic disciplines. There is a proliferation of journals, with new ones appearing almost every year, of which many are predatory: i.e. offering an easy path to publication in return for an upfront fee (more on predatory journals later).

Respected journals usually have some documented history, and therefore a set of metrics about their impact and visibility. They usually follow a strict peer-review process making them highly competitive.

This information can be available directly from the journal, or from aggregators where you can search a large number of journals and their metrics. One such resource is SHERPA RoMEO (<http://www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/index.php>), which is used by most UK universities to handle the archival of their staff's publications.

New journals are usually established to cover new areas of study or new perspectives that are emerging or growing. They might not be as impactful as older ones, but they could be a good place to publish if your topic is so new or unusual that it might not fit neatly into a long-lived journal.

As it is a very sought-after publication venue, getting your paper reviewed by a journal can mean a long process and a long wait. Editors will have to find suitable and willing reviewers (a scarce resource), then the manuscript will go out to them (usually 3, but could be more), comments will come back first to the editor and then to you and, if your work is not rejected outright, you will be (in most cases) asked to revise your manuscript to a various extent and resubmit it for further review together with a cover letter explaining how you addressed the reviewers' comments.

With such a large pool of journals available, it is important to identify those to target and to make sure they are genuine and rigorous.

Most journals (particularly those that are published by global publishing conglomerates such as Taylor & Francis, Springer, Elsevier, etc.) have websites/webpages where you can view information on their acceptance rate, average speed of editorial process and impact factor, and where you can see their most viewed and most downloaded articles. This will give you a sense of what they publish, of their readership, and of their standing.

Even if you or your institution don't have a subscription to the journal, you will be able to read the table of contents of recent issues. If, on the other hand, your institution has a subscription, you should also read some articles and use them as useful models to prepare your own.

Impact factor is another metric that is often used to assess the prestige of a journal. Impact factor is an index that reflects the mean number of yearly citations received by articles published in a certain journal. It is calculated periodically every two years by the bibliometric data analytics company Clarivate. Impact factor is often considered an important indicator of the reputation and impact of a journal, but it can be a problematic metric as journal articles in certain disciplines, or journals with a broader remit, will receive a much higher number of citations compared to those in smaller fields or on niche topics, which, despite lower impact factor, might still be of excellent scientific quality and outstanding reputation in their respective disciplines.

Impact factor has been widely criticised as a measure of a journal's academic quality, particularly when used as the only criterion.

→ It is also important to check the editorial information about a journal: Who is the editor-in-chief? Who are the associate editors? Are they established scholars? Do you recognise their names from the literature that you study/follow? Are they affiliated to a known university or other research institution?

→ If it is not clear who is responsible for the journal, then you might want to ask for another opinion about it (such as from a colleague or supervisor).

Journal special issues are also common opportunities to submit a paper and could be good opportunities to publish in a journal under a specially-themed issue. Special issues are usually guest-edited by scholars who are not regular editors for that journal and who wish to collect a set of articles on a particular topic. Special issues might mean a slightly faster submission-revisions process, and the opportunity for your article to appear in conjunction with related work.

Most serious journals have online submission systems, usually powered by their publishers. All the article information as well as the manuscript itself is submitted electronically. Such systems are also used by editors to manage the reviewing process.

→ Once you have identified the journal to submit to, carefully read the “Instructions to Authors” information that you will find on its webpage and that will provide you with clear instructions on how to prepare the paper (preferred language, but also formatting rules for sections, images, references, etc.), and how to submit it. To submit your article through an online submission system, you will usually need to create an account onto the system, linked to an email address and/or ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/>).

It sometimes happens that articles are “desk rejected” for a number of reasons. A desk reject is when a submission is rejected by a journal before going for external review, most often on grounds unrelated to scientific quality. For example, editorial assistants might desk reject a submitted article because it does not comply with a journal’s instructions to authors, or an editor might issue a desk reject if the submission is considered outside the scope of the journal. There can be more serious reasons for a desk reject, although more rare, such as a detection of plagiarism. While receiving a desk reject can be a startling and disappointing experience, in most cases it will be down to technical reasons, such as a poor fit with the journal’s aims and scope. In that case, the search for an alternative journal will continue.

If your submitted article goes out to peer reviewers and receives “revise and resubmit” feedback, you will be given a time frame within which to resubmit a revised version of your article. This time frame might vary depending on whether the required revisions will be deemed “major” or “minor”.

If you think that this time frame (for whatever reason) won’t be sufficient, contact the editor immediately to inform them. They might not be able to make an exception for you, or they might. In either case, it will help you to plan.

As you modify your paper to take into account the reviews, keep a log of what you are changing and which specific piece of feedback you are responding to. It will become a first draft of your cover letter, which will accompany the resubmission. Make sure to explain how you addressed the feedback, where exactly in the paper, and if you decide not to follow a reviewer’s suggestion dedicate a bit of work to write a convincing reason for it. A clearly structured table or bullet point list of revisions in response to feedback

can be a very useful thing to include, and some journals explicitly ask for such a document to be resubmitted with the revised article.

If/when your paper is accepted, you will be asked to do a final round of editorial revisions (usually with the help of a production editor), and to provide information on copyright transfer. Most journals these days publish under two possible frameworks: “green” open access or “gold” open access.

“Green” open access is when you do not pay money to publish in the journal, and you agree to transfer the copyright of the paper to the journal. The article will be available to those who have a subscription to the journal (either a personal one or through their university/company) or who pay to download it, but the journal will allow you to file a pre-publication version of it (the final version of the text, before production) on an institutional or scholarly repository, usually after an embargo period.

“Gold” open access is when you (or, more commonly, your institution) pay to retain copyright and make the article accessible to anyone directly from the journal’s repository under a Creative Commons License. In Ireland, universities in the IREL consortium of research libraries (<https://irel.ie>) pay annual fees to several publishers so that authors affiliated with them can submit to many journals and publish article as gold open access without additional charges.

If you think that your paper has high potential in terms of impact (for example, as a major case study, or as a resource for a category of professionals who might not have access to journal subscriptions), it is worth asking your university which journals are covered by their open access agreements, and consider submitting to one of them. If the journal you are targeting is not covered by such an agreement, it is worth seeking available funds, from your university or from a research project, to pay the article processing fee (APF) for gold open access. If your publication is funded by a research project, there might be funding there that has been dedicated to this purpose.

The Boole Library at UCC offers ample information on open access on their research support website (<https://libguides.ucc.ie/OAatucc?menu>).

In recent years, there has been a proliferation of Open Access journals, which publish all articles as open access and operate with reduced or no financial and legal barriers: if you are targeting an open access journal do a little research:

→ Are they legitimate publications? Are they managed by a professional or scholarly association?

→ Does the editorial board include respected scholars?

If there is no information about the editorial board, or if it isn’t clear who oversees that journal, be wary and seek additional advice.

It is useful to research the journal on the Directory of Open Access Journals (<https://doaj.org/>), however always add additional checks as the directory has been known to include some predatory journals.

→ Be very careful to avoid predatory journals! They are those journals that unscrupulously prey on authors guaranteeing fast publication for high prices, without presenting the credentials of reputed journals. There is a flourishing market out there, and a few lists (known as “blacklists”) have been produced in recent years to identify such journals.

The Wikipedia page on Predatory open access publishing (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Predatory_publishing) is a good place to start.

If you are approached by a journal that you have never heard of, spend some time seeking information on it, both online and through trusted colleagues.

Finally, it might be a good idea to volunteer to review for a journal in your field: not only it is good practice to keep up to date with the literature in your field, but it is also a “good citizen” thing to do, as the number of submissions is constantly increasing and the number of available reviewers is scarce. You can approach a journal’s editor or associate editor with a polite email mentioning your interest in reviewing and adding all the information that will help them understand which are your strong topics and expertise (e.g. link to your webpage, providing your CV, etc.).

Or if you meet a journal editor at a conference, mention your interest in reviewing and that you will follow up by sending them an email. They will surely appreciate it.

3. Conferences

Conferences can be great venues for publication as they also bring with them the possibility to meet people and to network. They can give great visibility to you and your work.

However, there are various types of conferences and not all of them will lead to a full, peer-reviewed publication. Here are some examples of models according to which conferences could operate:

- Submission is by sending in an abstract only, and this is what gets quickly reviewed, then - if accepted - you present the full paper. Only the abstract gets published.
- Submission is an abstract and this goes out for peer review; if accepted, the full paper to be produced for the conference presentation gets published.
- The full paper is submitted and peer reviewed. Accepted papers are published and presented.
- The full paper is submitted with a journal-like process of revisions and resubmissions. Accepted papers get published and presented.

Criteria for choosing a conference are similar to those described earlier for journals: it could be the conference where most of the scholars on a topic publish, or where many of the papers you cite in your work have appeared, or it could be a less well-known conference that has the advantage of addressing specifically a niche or uncommon topic.

→ Check the conference website and/or call for papers for information on the editorial process: how does the peer-review process work? Within which time frame?

→ Check previous editions of the conference and where the papers from them are: are they published? And if so in what form? As a book of proceedings or as a special issue, etc.? Which publisher is publishing them? Will they be assigned ISBN or ISSN numbers?
→ If the papers presented at the conference are not published in an archival manner (e.g. as an edited book or a special issue), is there the possibility for you to publish them elsewhere after the conference? Under which copyright agreement will they be published?

The same quality checks recommended for journals apply to conferences in terms of scholarly relevance:

→ Who is the conference general chair? Is there a dedicated scientific programme chair? Who is in the scientific committee? Who is behind the conference? Is the conference endorsed by a scientific group or professional association?
→ What is the acceptance rate? Does it look like they accept all submissions or like they have a selection process based on merit?

As with journals, there are many predatory conferences that are run to make money with little or no care for quality or scholarship.

If you cannot find answers to the questions above about a conference, or if the answers you find are unclear or dubious, consult with a trusted colleague.

Another example of predatory conferences are “multi-conferences” that bring together dozens of tracks on topics that appear completely unrelated to each other, guarantee certain publication, and charge a hefty fee with no evidence of rigorous peer-review. In general, those who ask for money in order to accept the paper without peer-review (rather than for registration after the paper has been reviewed and accepted) are also to be avoided upfront.

→ Again, if a particular conference catches your eye and you are not sure about its standing, seek additional advice from a trusted colleague in your field.

4. Book Chapters

Book chapters are usually solicited by other researchers putting together an edited book or handbook. Sometimes, editors will target specific people who they know work on a certain topic, other times there will be calls for chapters issued publicly (for example through mailing lists) to which you can respond with an abstract or chapter proposal. Books can take a long time to get published (at least a year if not two), at the same time book chapters allow the author to work on narratives that can be more speculative and reflexive than a journal paper. Also, if the book is in a seldom-explored area, it has the potential to become a key reference and a chapter in such a volume could get good exposure.

→ Again, to ascertain what the credentials of an edited book are spend some time to check who is driving the process: who is editing the book? Are they an expert on the topic?
→ Who is going to publish the book? Or to which publishers are the editors planning to submit the book proposal?

→ What peer-review and editorial process have the editors planned? Do they have a timeline in mind? The more detailed the editors' plan is, the more likely your chapter will see the light of day within a reasonable timeframe, and under the aegis of a reputed publisher.

5. Writing a Monograph

Writing an entire book can be a daunting task, but it is also one of the ways to publish something substantial (such as your doctoral dissertation) in a more accessible format, or to publish about substantial body of work as one major output. In certain disciplines, for example within the humanities, monographs are a scholar's most regarded published outputs.

In order to publish a monograph, you need to obtain a book contract with a publisher. In order to obtain such contract, you need first to prepare a book proposal according to the guidelines that that publisher has set out and submit it to a relevant editor.

Each publisher usually has information on their webpage about how to prepare and submit a book proposal.

Most book proposals will have to include:

- An abstract about what the book is about
- A title
- A table of contents
- One or more sample chapters
- Information about the author(s) and editor(s)
- Explanation of which gap in the market the book fills (including in relation to competing publications) and who are the intended readers.

Again, your knowledge of the literature can help you choose a reputed publisher to submit your book proposal to. A lot of publishers have "book series" dedicated to a certain topic or discipline. If you have read good books by good academic authors, check out who published them and under which book series.

Publishers will have information on their book series online, and you can also find out who edits the series.

→ It is a good idea to contact the editor of a topic/series to ask if a book such as the one you have in mind would be of interest to them, before preparing a full proposal. If they respond positively to your idea, then proceed with preparing and submitting a full proposal.

Book proposals are usually sent out for review to established academics in the area, and they can come back with different feedback. A common scenario is that the commissioning editor will request that there are some slight modifications to the planned book content to address important issues flagged by reviewers (such as changing slightly the order of chapters, or adding one to discuss something important). If the publisher is happy with a proposal, they will offer you a contract and you will be able to submit the book for editorial checks and then production once it has been completed.

The contract will also outline the financial agreement you will have with the publisher in terms of royalties and proceeds from book sales.

→ Check out how good various publishers are in supporting authors after publication: will they market the book? Will they provide you with gratis copies that you will be able to use to advertise your work? Will they actively contact journals or magazines to review your book? Do they offer an eBook option?

As with journals and conferences, there also exist predatory publishers which solicit manuscripts (often for hefty fees) but have no credentials in the publishing world. Further good advice on how to identify a predatory publisher can be found at this useful website by Iowa State University Library (<http://instr.iastate.libguides.com/predatory/id>).

6. Writing a Chapter in a book you edit

Proposals for edited books will usually follow the format of those for monographs, with the exception that you will have to source other chapters as well as writing one or more yourself. Depending on others to submit chapters will also make the process longer.

→ Same recommendations outlined in Section 5 apply to finding a publisher and submitting an edited book proposal, and also the same warning about (you guessed it!) predatory publishers.

7. Workshops/Symposia

These could be useful events to participate in to get feedback on your work and gain visibility, particularly if the call for participation mentions that there are plans for a follow-up publication, such as a journal special issue or edited book.

→ Again, do some research on who is responsible for the event, to make sure it has academic relevance and, if you are in doubt after reading the call, ask the organisers about the follow-up publication plans, if any.

→ If they don't have publication plans, ask if you will be able to publish your paper elsewhere after the workshop.

8. Magazines

Magazine articles can be good vehicles to gain visibility and to direct readers to more of your research. Scientific magazines are usually lightly peer-reviewed (by editors), and normally publish shorter articles than a journal and targeted to a more general audience. However, with magazines this could often mean pitching an idea to the editor first, rather than submitting a full article upfront. Again, find out who is the scientific editor of the magazine and direct any questions to them.

→ The checks to identify a suitable magazine are pretty much the same as those for journals, including locating a set of instructions for submitting article proposals.

→ Many scholarly magazines are published by professional bodies or societies, such as the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) or the American Psychological Association (APA), and are read by members. Identifying whether such an institution is behind a magazine in your field can be a useful way to assess their reputation and potential impact.

9. Blogs, Newsletters, Online Forums, DIY

In our Internet age, getting a piece of writing out there can be incredibly easy if all you want is to make a piece available to readers quickly and freely. You have options such as setting up your own blog, or website, or to contribute to a group blog, newsletter or other online forums.

Obviously, think carefully if this is the best way for you to publish something: it might mean no barriers to reaching it, but also little or no protection against someone taking your content and re-using it without permission and scruples. If what you are posting is a personal reflection, or short report then the risk is minimal, but if you choose to present part of your research findings in this way, carefully weigh the possible pros and cons. There also exist certain “midway” platforms where (working) papers can be made available without paywalls: from institutional repositories that Universities run, to commercial platforms such as Academia.edu and ResearchGate.

→ Check the terms and conditions that these platforms offer, and always be careful with publishing something there that has not been previously published elsewhere and that enjoys some intellectual property safeguard.

→ Prepare pre-publication versions of all your publications, most of which you will be able to share, for example through an institutional repository, once the embargo period has passed.

10. Think – Check – Submit!

Are you submitting your research to a trusted journal?

Publishing your research results is key to **advancing your discipline** – and your **career** – but with so many journals in your field, how can you be sure that you're choosing a **reputable, trustworthy** journal?

Tips to **confirm** a journal's credentials and decide if it will help you **reach** the right audience with your research, and make an **impact** on your career.

Take control of your career at
thinkchecksubmit.org

The <https://thinkchecksubmit.org/> initiative makes available some useful checklists to identify reputed publication venues (particularly journals).

→ If you are in doubt about a venue, use these checklists as well as asking trusted and more experienced colleagues.

List of Links

- ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/>
- <https://thinkchecksubmit.org/>
- Understanding Predatory Publishers, Iowa State University:
<http://instr.iastate.libguides.com/predatory/id>
- SHERPA/RoMEO, a directory for checking publisher copyright and self-archiving policies: <http://www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/index.php>
- Directory of Open Access Journals: <https://doaj.org>
- Open Access Support, UCC Boole Library:
<https://libguides.ucc.ie/OAatucc?menu>
- The IREL Consortium of Research Libraries in Ireland: <https://irel.ie>
- Wikipedia page on Predatory open access publishing:
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Predatory_publishing

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An experienced senior academic working across disciplines internationally, she has co-authored over one hundred refereed articles and two monographs, and has edited several books, collections and journal special issues. She has been scientific programme chair and associate editor for several prestigious conferences in her field, and is an Associate Aditor for the Computer-Supported Cooperative Work Journal (Springer Nature).

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